

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING READING

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Abstract: The use of authentic materials in teaching English as a foreign language can be highly effective in helping learners to improve their language skills. When used appropriately, authentic materials can provide learners with opportunities to develop their reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills by exposing them to natural language use in a variety of contexts. Using authentic materials can help to promote learner engagement and motivation, as well as foster a more authentic and meaningful learning experience. The aim of this thesis is to expose the efficient ways of using authentic material in reading skills.

Key words: skill, material, authentic, method, motivation, engage, material, students, online, read, practice, language, classroom.

The usage of authentic materials in foreign language teaching has a long history. For example, Henry Sweet, who taught and wrote in the late 19th century and is considered one of the first linguists, regularly used authentic texts in his books and was well aware of their potential advantages over his contrived sources. The advantage of natural, idiomatic text over artificial "methods" or "lines" is that it accurately reflects all features of the language.

Given the wide range of meanings associated with authenticity, it is not surprising that most teachers find the term ambiguous. Furthermore, it is impossible to start a meaningful discussion about the pros and cons of authenticity until you agree with what we are talking about. [1] Authenticity relates to the qualities bestowed on a text by the receiver, in that it is not seen as something inherent in a text itself, but

is imparted on it by the reader/listener [2] Authenticity relates to the language produced by a real speaker/writer for a real audience, conveying a real message [3]

When it comes to teaching reading skills to EFL learners, it is important to use authentic materials as much as possible. Authentic materials are materials that are taken from real-life situations, as opposed to materials that have been created specifically for the classroom. When selecting authentic materials to use in the classroom, it is important to consider the level of proficiency of your students. Some authentic materials may be too difficult for beginners, while others may be too simple for advanced students. It is important to find materials that are challenging, but not overwhelming, for your students. There are many sources of authentic materials online and in print. Some popular sources include news articles, magazines, movies, and TV shows. It is important to be selective when choosing materials, as not all materials are appropriate for the classroom. However, with a little bit of research, it is easy to find materials that are both interesting and relevant for your students. There are many benefits to using authentic materials in the classroom.

Initially, using authentic materials helps to improve students' language skills. Authentic materials are typically more interesting and engaging for students than traditional textbooks or worksheets. This means that students are more likely to pay attention and learn from them. [4] 'An authentic text is a stretch of real language, produced by a real speaker or writer for a real audience and designed to convey a real message of some sort.' Additionally, using authentic materials provides students with opportunities to practice their reading skills in a real-world context. This can be helpful in preparing them for future interactions with native speakers. Finally, using authentic materials can help to build students' cultural awareness. By exposing students to authentic materials from different cultures, teachers can help to broaden their students' understanding of the world. This can

be especially valuable for students who are studying English as a second language.

The best content to choose will depend on the student, their level of English, and the course content the teacher wants to focus on. It is also helpful to find out what your students are interested in. After all, if everyone is a fan of action movies, there's no point trying to captivate your students with a text about the latest sci-fi flick. Materials should reflect situations that students may encounter in an English-speaking environment. This will help students step into a world where English is the norm. One of the main ideas for using real materials in the classroom is to "expose" students to as much real language as possible. It has been argued that by taking a text out of its original context, it loses its authenticity.

The concept of authenticity is central to CLT as learners are exposed to the same languages as native speakers. Four types of authenticity within the classroom have been identified and in particular to the use of authentic texts:

1. Authenticity of the texts which we may use as input data for our students;
2. Authenticity of the learners' own interpretations of such texts;
3. Authenticity of tasks conducive to language learning;
4. Authenticity of the actual social situation of the classroom language. [5]

The different types of text mean that will find it easier to find something that interests students and may even encourage more reading or reading for pleasure. The advantage of using an entire newspaper or magazine in class over copying an article is that students can actually choose what they want to read. The more a student reads, the better they will read, and not only will their language level improve, but their confidence will also increase. If the text is of interest to the student, it can also relate to their own experience. One of the goals of Authentic materials is to help students respond in the same way that foreign language speakers respond in their native language (L1).

The negative aspects of authentic materials are that they can be too culturally

biased, often a good knowledge of cultural background is required when reading, as well as too many structures are mixed, causing lower levels of problems when decoding the texts [6]. Understudies regularly bring duplicates of daily paper articles (in specific the tabloids) or tune verses to the classroom, inquiring to interpret them after having looked up each word within the lexicon and not caught on a single word.

Overall, the use of authentic materials can be highly effective in helping students to improve their language skills. When used appropriately, these materials can provide learners with exposure to the language in its natural context, help to improve their understanding of the language and create a more immersive and meaningful learning experience. There is no doubt that the use of authentic materials in the classroom can be highly effective in helping students to improve their language skills. When used appropriately, authentic materials can provide learners with opportunities to develop their not only reading, but also their listening, speaking, and writing skills by exposing them to natural language use in a variety of contexts.

When handling authentic materials, students feel more secure and more in control as long as the teacher provides them with pedagogical support. According to the needs of the students, authentic materials should be used. ability, with appropriate tasks being assigned where complete understanding is not crucial. One solution to the issues caused by challenging authentic texts is to simplify them in accordance with the learner's level.

Another possible solution is to give text-related tasks. They are three basic types:
Pre-reading: used not just to test or compensate for linguistic/socio-cultural inadequacies but also used to activate existing schemata;

While-reading: used to encourage the learner to be a flexible, active reader and also to promote a dialogue between reader and writer;

Post-reading: often are questions that follow a text, used to test understanding but

sometimes a good schema will be enough. [7] Challenges of writing process and the ways of overcoming them.

The text can be made more approachable by eliciting students' prior knowledge in pre-reading discussions, reviewing new vocabulary before reading, and then asking students to carry out tasks that are within their capabilities, rather than simply simplifying the text by changing its language. proficiency before they start intensive reading, such as skimming to get the main idea or scanning for specific information. Additionally, the reading strategy must be genuine. Students should read the text in a manner that is appropriate for the purpose for which it is being read, the type of text, and how people typically read it. This means that only situations that would occur outside of the classroom—situations where reading aloud would be appropriate—will be used. Reading is a purposeful activity. The purpose of reading guides the reader's selection of texts. The purpose of reading also determines the appropriate approach to reading comprehension.

The benefits of exposing students to real language in a real context have been discussed in relation to the use of authentic materials in the classroom. Utilizing authentic materials also had the benefit of being highly motivating and providing an understanding, which will motivate readers to read more. They are also very adaptable (they can be used in different ways to promote different skills), reflect changes in language usage, have a wide range of text types, and can be updated as well as used multiple times. Anything can be used as authentic material, but the Internet is one of the best sources for improving reading because it is so easy to access a wealth of diverse content.

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